

Online user study

Study Script (1 hour)

Hello, my name is [name]. I am from Oregon State University and we are conducting a study on designing better tools to improve diversity and inclusion in OSS projects. Thank you for taking the time to participate and help us advance the research. As you can already guess, I will be reading from a script to provide consistent information to you and the other participants.

Please note that all information collected will be anonymized and remain confidential. No identifiable information will be collected. More information about privacy can be found in the informed consent form we sent you. You have the option to withdraw from the study at any time, and if you choose to do so, all the data that has been collected up until that point will be deleted.

[Send informed consent and get approval]

Before we start: In order to not interrupt the performance, please set your cell phone to silent and please do not discuss any details of the study with others to maintain information consistency among participants.

If you have any questions at any time, feel free to ask.

We will be audio and screen recording this session for transcription purposes, so please let us know if you consent to be recorded.

Thank you, I just started the recording as you can see in the top left corner

[Start recording here]

The study has four parts:

- (1) A pre-study survey
- (2) Study session
- (3) A post-study survey

As a token of appreciation, we will send you a \$50 gift card.

Do you have any questions so far?

[Wait for questions]

Let's start with a pre-study survey. [send the form via chat]

I just sent you a link in the chat, please fill out the form [LINK](#)

And let me know when you're finished.

[study part]

Now, let's move on to the dashboard part of the study. I'll send you a link and login credentials through the chat.

Link: LINK

Credentials:

Username: g*****

Password: *****

Please open the link provided in the chat and log in with the credentials we sent you. Once you're logged in, please share your screen with us.

[wait]

Now, I'll be guiding you through the set of dashboards. As you navigate, please think aloud and share your thoughts with us. I'll ask you a few questions for each dashboard.

Just a reminder, we're not evaluating you, we're simply interested in your experience using the dashboards. Please use the dashboard to respond to these questions.

[dashboard starts here]

(1) Please navigate to the Contributor retention trends tab on the top right menu.

Please, take a minute to look over the dashboard, scroll up and down, and look at the different visualizations and their titles to have an idea about the content of each visualization. We ask you to think aloud while doing so.

Does anything stand out to you?

Ok, on the top right, there is a clock icon with [say the date is there], please check that it is set to the last 5 years

DEFINE LEFT (last 6 months no contribution)

MIGHT BE LEAVING (last 3 months no contribution)

New contributors start contributing in the last 6 months and never contributed before

1. How would you describe the attraction and retention trend of men compared to women? How would you use this information?
2. What is the percentage of contributors from Akvelon, Inc. who left the project last year? How would you use this information?
3. Can you point out the women contributors with more than 40 contributions who might be leaving? What is their affiliation? How would you use this information?
4. Who is the most recent woman newcomer to the project? What is her affiliation? When was her first contribution date? How would you use this information?

Thank you, now I will send you a Google document link. Please open the link and keep your screen sharing on. We will use this document to ask you some questions.

LINK FOR QUESTIONS: LINK

Thank you for responding to these questions.

Thank you, please select the dashboard tab now

(3) Please navigate to the communication tab, and select Now select by affiliation.

Please, take a minute to look over the dashboard, scroll up and down, and look at the different visualizations and their titles to have an idea about the content of each visualization. We ask you to think aloud while doing so.

Does anything stand out to you?

Please navigate to the communication network visualization. There is a legend for the different colors. You can also zoom in to see the name of the actual contributor. You can click on one of the contributors and drag them to see how connected they are to the network. You can also find this information in the readme.

In the last 30 days,

1. Which affiliation has had on average the longest time to have their PR merged? How would you use this information?
2. Are there any subgroups that are not connected to the main network in the pull request communication network? Pick an example, and please tell me which affiliations are involved. How would you use such information?

In the last 7 days,

Knowing that the edges reflect the connections between different contributors.

3. Who is the most connected contributor? What affiliation? How would you use such information?

(4) Please navigate to the communication tab and select by gender.

We define pull requests that need attention as pull requests that have not received comments from other contributors or reviewers

In the last 30 days,

1. What is the oldest pull request that did not receive any comments? Who is the author? their gender and affiliation? How would you use this information?

Thank you, now I will send you a Google document link. Please open the link and keep your screen sharing on. We will use this document to ask you some questions.

LINK FOR QUESTIONS: LINK

Thank you, please select the dashboard tab now

(1) Please select the “types of contributions”, here you will see two subtabs (gender and affiliation). Please select the “gender” tab.

Please, take a minute to look over the dashboard, scroll up and down, and look at the different visualizations and their titles to have an idea about the content of each visualization. We ask you to think aloud while doing so.

Does anything stand out to you?

Please let us know when you are ready.

1. Can you compare these two visualizations, the number of contributors by gender and the pull request count by gender? How would you use this information?
2. Could you please describe the evolution of issues over time by gender? How would you use this information?
3. How do the days to first attention to issues differ by gender? How would you use this information?

(2) Please navigate to the “types of contributions” tab again and this time, select “by affiliation”.

In the past 90 days,

1. What are the top three affiliations in your project in terms of the number of contributors? How would you use this information?
2. Can you compare these two visualizations, the number of contributors by affiliation and the pull request count by affiliation? How would you use this information?
3. Could you describe the evolution of StackOverflow activity by affiliation? How would you use this information?

Thank you, now I will send you a Google document link. Please open the link and keep your screen sharing on. We will use this document to ask you some questions.

LINK TO QUESTIONS: LINK

Now that you got familiarized yourself with the set of dashboards. Please use the link I am sending to you in the chat to fill out the post-study survey. It's the last questionnaire I promise 😊. Some of the questions are repeated from the survey you filled in at the beginning of the study. Do not worry about what you answered before. We want to collect the information again after interacting with the dashboard.

Link: LINK

Please let me know when you are done.

Thank you again for participating in the study, we really appreciate your time and insights. In the coming days, we will be sending you a gift card as a token of appreciation. Is the email you provided in the survey a good email to send the gift card to?

[wait]

Thank you, I will stop recording now. Have a wonderful rest of your day!

The end!

In-person user study

Study Script (1 hour)

Hello, my name is [name]. I am from Oregon State University and we are conducting a study on designing better tools to improve diversity and inclusion in OSS projects. Thank you for taking the time to participate and help us advance the research. As you can already guess, I will be reading from a script to provide consistent information to you and the other participants.

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[Send informed consent and get approval]

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[Start recording here]

The study has 3 parts:

- (1) A pre-study survey
- (2) Navigating a dashboard
- (3) A post-study survey

As a token of appreciation, we will send you a \$50 gift card.

Do you have any questions so far?

[Wait for questions]

Let's start with a pre-study survey. [send the form via chat]

I just sent you a link in the chat, please fill out the form

[LINK]

And let me know when you're finished.

[study part]

Now, let's move on to the dashboard part of the study. I'll send you a link and login credentials through the chat.

Link: LINK

Credentials:

Username: g*****

Password: *****

Please open the link provided in the chat and log in with the credentials we sent you. Once you're logged in, please share your screen with us.

[wait]

For each dashboard, you will watch a short tutorial and then I will ask you to explore the dashboard and to please think aloud while doing so.

Just a reminder, we're not evaluating you, we're simply interested in your experience using the dashboards.

The first dashboard is the Contributor retention trends, I'll start a short video tutorial now.

[play the video]

Thank you.

[dashboard starts here]

(1) Please navigate to the Contributor retention trends tab on the top right menu. Please take your time to explore the dashboard, scroll up and down, and look at the different visualizations. Please think aloud while doing so.

In this project, if this is available how will you use the dashboard?

Thank you, now I will send you a Google document link. Please open the link and keep your screen sharing on. We will use this document to ask you some questions.

LINK FOR QUESTIONS: LINK

Thank you for responding to these questions.

Thank you, please select the dashboard tab now

The second dashboard is the communication dashboard which contains two dashboards one by affiliation and one by gender.

I'll start a short video tutorial now.

[play the video]

Thank you

(2) Now, please navigate to the communication tab, and select Now select by affiliation.

Please take your time to explore the dashboard, scroll up and down, and look at the different visualizations. Please think aloud while doing so.

In this project, if this is available how will you use the dashboard?

(3) Please navigate to the communication tab and select by gender.

Please take your time to explore the dashboard, scroll up and down, and look at the different visualizations. Please think aloud while doing so.

In this project, if this is available how will you use the dashboard?

Thank you, now I will send you a Google document link. Please open the link and keep your screen sharing on. We will use this document to ask you some questions.

LINK FOR QUESTIONS:LINK

Thank you, please select the dashboard tab now

The third dashboard is the types of contributions dashboard which contains two dashboards one by gender and one by affiliation.

I'll start a short video tutorial now.

[play the video]

Thank you

(4) Now please select the “types of contributions”, here you will see two subtabs (gender and affiliation). Please select the “gender” tab.

Please take your time to explore the dashboard, scroll up and down, and look at the different visualizations. Please think aloud while doing so.

In this project, if this is available how will you use the dashboard?

(5) Please navigate to the “types of contributions” tab again and this time, select “by affiliation”.

Please take your time to explore the dashboard, scroll up and down, and look at the different visualizations. Please think aloud while doing so.

In this project, if this is available how will you use the dashboard?

Thank you, now I will send you a Google document link. Please open the link and keep your screen sharing on. We will use this document to ask you some questions.

LINK TO QUESTIONS: LINK

Now that you got familiarized yourself with the set of dashboards. Please use the link I am sending to you in the chat to fill out the post-study survey. It's the last questionnaire I promise 😊. Some of the questions are repeated from the survey you filled in at the beginning of the study. Do not worry about what you answered before. We want to collect the information again after interacting with the dashboard.

Link: LINK.

Please let me know when you are done.

Thank you again for participating in the study, we really appreciate your time and insights. In the coming days, we will be sending you a gift card as a token of appreciation. Is the email you provided in the survey a good email to send the gift card to?

[wait]

Thank you, I will stop recording now. Have a wonderful rest of your day!

The end!

